

**INTRODUCING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO
QUANTITATIVE MEASURES**

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Introduction to length measurement units is studied in elementary grades. For example: step, step, make, and hakoza. Length, product dimensions and distances are measured with these. These units are still used today.

It would be useful if modern mathematics used these units to explain the difference between the old and current units of measurement during the lesson. Because with this, we need to preserve the units that are disappearing without being used.

The role of teaching elementary students quantitative concepts in the development of thinking skills in mathematics lessons is great. We will dwell on some types of such issues below.

Units of length are introduced to 1st graders by the end of the 2nd quarter, beginning with information about the decimeter. Some exercises can be done using the decimeter module. All these exercises help children to master the numbers well. First, they are taught the length of the matchbox and the length of the pencil. For this purpose, the use of exact centimeters will be mentioned first.

They can make a number of models per centimeter, for this they need to cut a long strip from a sheet of checkered paper equal to one square, and then cut a strip of 1 cm from it.

The children make a sign that they are equal by placing the tiles on top of each other. The teacher says that each of these squares is a module of a centimeter.

Using the centimeter model:

1) Measure the given section

2) Making a cut of a given length.

At first, many length measurements were used in our Uzbek people, and our people used them fully.

Nowadays, they are losing their power. Instead, the length measurements discussed above are being used.

However, not all of them have lost their power. Gas, width, karich, kuloch, stone, step, mile, address, wood, farsang, adim, mayin and other words.

At that time, these words were considered a certain unit of measurement. They are divided into groups.

- 1) relative to the length of the thing
- 2) in relation to the length of the distance

The word "Karachi" has been used in all interactions between the people for centuries. We still use this measure. 1 inch = 20 cm.

The word kuloch is used when something measures the length of an object. It refers to the amount between two hands.

For example: two cubits of rope, five cubits. Ears are not different. The word address is also expressed as the distance between two places expressed in vague measure.

Children form the idea that the length measure is a property that describes the duration, the dimensions of an object. Children can correctly identify the relationships longer, wider, wide - narrow, high - low, thick - thin.

The following lesson can be used to introduce quantitative measurements to elementary school students.

Place several children around the table and give each a small stick. The players are blindfolded and something is placed in front of each of them: a jug, a teapot, a can, a box, etc. The task of the players is to roughly estimate what is in front of them, what material it is made of, and its length in cm.

We check the first measurement, it is a centimeter, we determine how many times a centimeter is located in the second measurement and we call it a decimeter: $1\text{dm} = 10\text{ cm}$. A disimeter measure is made of cardboard, one side of which is of one color, and the other side is divided into centimeters and fixed on a thin wire.

References

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